

The Origin of Life

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Article Text

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Current situation.

By the beginning of the 21st century, this question seemed to have been definitively resolved; the concept of competition of reactions was adopted as its foundation.

The Origin of Life, Modern Theory.

The concept of modern "official science" states that the first living organisms appeared as a result of processes of organic molecule complication in Earth's primordial ocean, arising from competition between different reactions. In the course of this hypothesized phenomenon, from several possible chemical reactions with initial substances, the existing physical conditions of the environment made necessary a selection of reactions whose outcome were increasingly complex and larger molecules.

Thus, on the basis of chemical processes with non-living initial substances, as a result of a long series of reactions that took place under the unusual physical conditions of the "young Earth," the first elements of living matter were formed.

This is how the process of the origin of life on Earth is currently formulated by official science.

Objections to the Concept of "Life from Non-Life"

Academic biologists see fundamental obstacles to reducing all phenomena and processes of cell biology to the concepts of physics and chemistry.

The reason: there are several concepts in cell biology that have no counterpart in physical and chemical phenomena and processes:

- control;
- transcription.

Furthermore, there is no analogy to the concept of information in them (Ref. 1).

Possible Answers to These Questions:

1) The Concept of "Expanding the Boundaries of Physics and Chemistry"

Currently (the 2010s), representatives of the natural sciences — physicists and chemists — acknowledge that a number of contradictions exist in science. Currently (the 2010s), representatives of the natural sciences — physicists and chemists — acknowledge that within these sciences there are no studied phenomena or occurrences corresponding to the phenomena and occurrences of life. From their point of view, this merely indicates that contemporary knowledge of physics and chemistry is incomplete. To explain the phenomena of life from the perspective of these sciences, it is necessary to expand their field of knowledge; more specifically, to discover and confirm through practical testing new physical and chemical laws and phenomena. These new discoveries would make it possible to explain all phenomena of the living from the perspective of the "exact" natural sciences, and thereby encompass all natural phenomena — both non-living and living — within a unified theoretical knowledge, well-confirmed by practice.

2) The Concept of "The Origin of Life on Earth as the Result of the Evolution of Even Smaller Organisms"

The serious differences in the principles of existence and development of non-living and living matter, taking into account the concept of the scales of matter in the organization of the Universe (the theory of the infinite nesting of matter), lead to the assumption that the most primitive (smallest in size) living organisms known to us (precellular organisms, RNA organisms) appeared as a result of the activity of even smaller organisms. Colonies of such organisms, conducting active vital activity, "generated" the smallest of the organisms known to us.

It thus appears that "life can only arise from life," and that "living organisms consist of elements of non-living matter and something else" — these concepts, seemingly long since discarded and refuted (vitalism, idealism), are once again becoming relevant.

3) The Concept of the Extraterrestrial Origin of Life (Panspermia)

Currently, the hypothesis that the first living organisms were not formed on Earth but were brought from space, for example, by meteorites, has not been completely dismissed. This hypothesis does not answer the question "How did life originate?" but rather shifts the location of this event from the surface of planet Earth to another place in the Universe.

Literature:

1. Shkundina, F. B. (2016). History and Methodology of Biology. Moscow: Knizhny Dom "Universitet", pp. 163–165. ISBN 978-5-91304-686-4.

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